

WAYS TO EXPAND OPPORTUNITIES FOR DISTANCE EDUCATION
FOR SCHOOLCHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract: In the article, the existing barriers to distance education for students with musculoskeletal disorders and effective ways to overcome them, pedagogues (educators, teachers, additional education) practical experiences of the activities of "teachers" in the educational process, it is revealed that special preparation of both sides is necessary for working in a new model of education - distance education.

Keywords: distance education, cerebral palsy, modern digital educational system, information technologies, web services, online tools.

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In modern society, in connection with the rapid development of information and communication technologies and the gradual decline in computers and other gadgets of this type, informatization and digitalization in the field of education, increased professional and personal mobility, economic changes, and especially the widespread coronavirus pandemic in 2020, the demand for distance learning from the traditional format of Education has increased, and these changes have shown The special socio-legal status of children with disabilities necessitates the provision of guarantees for obtaining education, including in the context of integrated education. To implement these priorities, it is necessary to take into account international experience, which is reflected in a number of international mainly normative documents, in particular: conventions "on the rights of the child", "on the rights of the disabled", "on Human Rights", "on the right of the mentally disabled", the ban on discrimination against children, the full involvement of a child with An important role in this regard is played by the implementation of large-scale reforms aimed at inclusive development in New Uzbekistan on the basis of the principle "for human dignity", that is, ensuring equal rights and opportunities for all segments of the population [1].

Analysis of literature on the subject (Literature review). Due to the fact that children with disabilities in the musculoskeletal system have a number of specific features, including increased fatigue, weakening of mental processes, difficulties in switching from one activity to another, in addition, due to the fact that the range of

intellectual disorders ranges from normal to severe levels of mental development, establishing their distance learning will facilitate their educational processes (I. Yu. Levchenko, O.G. Prikladka). The effectiveness of lesson processes when conducting special education with children of cerebral palsy depends on the competence of the pedagogue (A. A. Beybaradskikh, A.A. Verxazena, E.S. Kalmykova, R.V. Ovcharova and others). In modern pedagogic psychology, the focus is on reflecting the role of the subject-subject relationship and the student's relationship to the teacher (A. A. Rean and others).

Research Methodology (Research Methodology). Methodologically, students with disabilities in the musculoskeletal system and the problems that arise in their distance learning have been studied through methods such as the review and analytical study of pedagogic, medical and special psychosocial literature. As we all know, fundamental changes are taking place in the field of education in subsequent years. These include new information technologies, web services, online tools, the emergence and rapid growth of interactive learning trends. Distance education, which until recently was practically not used in educational institutions, became the main form of Education overnight, and students with special needs showed their influence on education. This is due to the fact that the education of students with cerebral palsy needs practical orientation, the use of materials that stimulate the visual, personal visual and tactical communication with the teacher [2]. In addition, children's cerebral palsy (BMF) is a set of disorders that affect a person's movement, balance, and correct posture. Children with cerebral palsy may have problems such as muscle weakness, restriction of movements, slowness and instability. There is a possibility that they will also have difficulty maintaining balance. Teaching children with cerebral palsy has its own characteristics that must be taken into account when organizing and conducting classes. The range of intellectual disorders in children with cerebral palsy can be at different levels: from normal levels of mental development to severe levels of mental retardation. From this, children with cerebral palsy, whose mental development is at a normal level in public school, study in the distance learning mode [3].

Features of teaching children with cerebral palsy: -the main manifestations of cerebral palsy are slowness and unformed motor skills and abilities. Motor in some children targeted actions. Often children also have tremor-tremors of the fingers and tongue. This is most clearly expressed by targeted actions (for example, when writing). A decrease in the number of contacts with others leads to the formation of a number of negative characteristic features: moral, volitional. Such children do not know how to overcome difficulties, subordinate their actions to certain requirements and rules. They make it difficult to organize their activities, organize

it and act. When organizing the educational process, it is necessary to take into account the features of the development of the cognitive and personal spheres. E.A.As Lukov noted, distance education is a kind of educational process of shaping knowledge, skills and abilities that provide interactive interaction between teachers and students.

In the modern system of digital education, information technology allows not only to solve educational problems, but also helps to implement the functions of Correction and development of education at different levels. In addition, information technologies often provide the most convenient format for cerebral cerebral palsy students to use educational resources, the form of presenting an electronic assignment itself is of interest to the child. Students with cerebral cerebral palsy are faced with a number of barriers to the use of distance education. Not all students with this type of disability can use standard equipment and software in the learning process, which means the need to adapt them to special educational needs. Therefore, the lack of proper organization of a convenient educational place in the organization of distance education, the child's parents are not provided with the child not only with computer equipment, but also with individual technical means of rehabilitation, auxiliary devices; parents need to leave the learning process uncontrolled, and not all of the teachers in the process of education, it is almost impossible for students to pass the vocational training exam at a distance; failure to draw up the lesson schedule of a student with a defect in the musculoskeletal system taking into account their individual capabilities, not taking into account the degree of its activity and functionality during the day (for example, the greatest activity of a child when taking medications can go from the first half of the day to the second half); losing the network. The biggest enemy of online knowledge acquisition is the slow operation of internet providers or the interruption of communication. In this situation, students have problems such as their desire to receive education is fading or causing them to become nervous.

There is a set of measures to eliminate the scale of such problems. To the sentence of these, first of all, it is necessary to revise the role, functions of the teacher "behind the screen" and the persons who directly help the child, clarify the functional capabilities of the auxiliary persons who will be next to the child in the process of distance education. For a teacher who is able to organize a child's activities in a distance format, it is one of the most effective ways to avoid situations such as emotional discomfort, dissatisfaction with oneself, fear of failure, as well as to increase the level of professional competence of pedogogs in the field of conducting advanced training courses and working with students with disabilities. Cerebral cerebral palsy conducting distance classes with schoolchildren

is basically the most effective way to organize in a small group (up to 5 people). Considering that recently there has been a tendency to increase the number of children in the classroom, distance learning requires dividing the class into two or three subgroups, respectively, involving several teachers in the work.

Analysis and Results (Analysis and results) A. A. Rean or. L. According to Kolominsky, it is impossible to consider not only the methods of education and upbringing of healthy children, but also students with any disabilities without paying attention to their communicative processes. Pedagogic communication is an important part of the pedagogic process. The specificity of such communication today is its mediation by information and communication means. [3]

Indeed, the use of modern technologies further expands the possibilities of today's education. Distance education, in contrast to traditional education, is also achieving a cost reduction in time, leading to a significant development of the educational process. As an example, we can say that in the online lesson jaroyon in schools we can see the benefits of using multimedia tools and interactive programs for students in:

- to enrich the impressions of students, to increase the speed of assimilation of information;
- increase the productivity of the teacher and avoid excessive expenses;
- performs the possibility of performing laboratory through virtual laboratories;
- reduce the time to increase the speed of learning.

Multimedia tools create the following comfort in the course of the lesson:

- a) to the perfect learning of the lesson being passed;
- b) increases interest by losing boredom in class;
- c) time saving and cost reduction;
- g) the object under study remains in the reader's memory for a long time and increases the chances of being able to apply it due to its proximity to practice.

In addition, through multimedia tools, it is possible to make a production or technological process using modern technical equipment when performing virtual laboratory work on a computer.

Yu. Levchenko, O.G. Prihodko's studies show that children with cerebral palsy have a high dynamics of the occurrence of physiological and intellectual strains signs of existing disability (cerebral palsy, hearing, vision, speech, etc.);

- academic performance (bad, average, good, active, passive);
- the pace of work in the lesson (SECN, medium, fast);
- general training of the student in science (passive, medium, active);

- attitude to different forms of work (preference for dialogue, preference for working with illustrative material, preference for discussing questions on the topic of the lesson, etc.);

- communication skills (weak, medium, high);

- emotionality (weak, medium, high);

- the ability to use technical means of teaching (weak, medium, good level).

b) the topic of the lesson, the purpose of the lesson:

- selection of materials (audio-video) for the lesson;

- after class, the student must understand, remember, know and be able to do the subject;

- determination of the amount of material available to the student, identification of interesting facts on the topic of the lesson;

- inclusion of a health stabilizing component in the composition of the lesson (heating, reflection technique, prevention of visual fatigue);

- preparation of a technological map of the lesson [4].

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, it is worth saying that the modern digital education system defines the principle of equal use of full-quality education, regardless of the health of students with limited physical activity. One of the ways to implement this requirement is, of course, to increase the scale of reforms in distance education. It should be noted that the educational system of this format is not only limited to a certain category of students with disabilities, but also has the opportunity to bring such experience to all participants in the educational process in the presence of technical conditions. Observation of a student with cerebral cerebral palsy allows you to track his individual cognitive activity, independence, effectiveness of activity, dynamics of the student's development, stability of the main manifestations of personal characteristics in the learning process, identify strengths and weaknesses. It allows you to evaluate it not only from the point of view of educational activity, but also according to personal manifestations, which is especially important in solving educational problems.

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